

GCAQE Closing Speech

Keith Taylor

Green MEP for South East England, London, UK

Corresponding author:

Keith Taylor

keith.taylor@europarl.europa.eu

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ABSTRACT

Keith Taylor, Green MEP for the South East, delivered the closing speech at the International Aircraft Cabin Air Conference on Wednesday 20 September 2017. The conference, at Imperial College London, was hosted by The Global Cabin Air Quality Executive (GCAQE) in association with Pall Aerospace, Unite the Union, the British Professional Pilots union (PPU), and the University of Stirling. The two-day event brought together industry experts, cabin crew unions, and researchers to discuss the health concerns surrounding passenger and crew air supply contamination feared to be responsible for several deaths of pilots and crew and hundreds of incidents where pilots have fallen ill, sometimes at the controls. Frequent flyers and young children could also be affected. Earlier that week, EasyJet announced its plans to fit filters, manufactured by Pall Aerospace, to its cabin air systems in a move seen as an acknowledgment of the health concerns surrounding 'aerotoxic syndrome' – which has been long been denied by airlines. Keith Taylor is a member of both the European Parliament's Environment and Public Health and Transport and Tourism Committees.

Closing speech

Good afternoon Ladies and Gentlemen, I'm Keith Taylor, the Green MEP for South East England and it is a pleasure to be here. I'd like to thank the organizers at GCAQE for inviting me to speak with you all at the end of this important conference.

It has been very eye-opening for me to learn about some of the issues you've been discussing here over the past two days and I hope that the outcome of getting you all together is that it will be a useful springboard for action

to continue to tackle some of the biggest challenges ahead on improving cabin air quality.

Some of you have first-hand experience of the impact contaminated air can have and you can truly appreciate the urgency with which this issue needs to be addressed.

But I also understand there are some stakeholders vital to moving forward on this issue still absent from the discussion and this is perhaps one of the greatest obstacles to making flights safer for the crew and passengers alike.

Using bleed air from the engine in the cabin and cockpit enables passengers to breathe on board an aircraft, and this is an approach that has been used by the aviation industry for decades. But since the outset, information has been available to the industry - as uncovered by the US military in the 1950s - that there are adverse effects associated with exposure to heated engine oils.

Despite the risks, the civil aviation industry opted for this ventilation system and in the past 30 years especially, it has become increasingly evident that this was a dangerous choice.

This is because there is no filtration process in place between the bleed air from the engine and the cabin, and indeed because the engine seals leak, low levels of contamination have been witnessed on many flights and more large scale 'fume events' or toxic leakages have also been reported, as explained by some of the speakers at this conference.

The issue of exposure is very complicated - there can be both short-term and long-term impacts and the symptoms are wide ranging - from blurred vision and dizziness, to nausea, vomiting, respiratory difficulties, irritation to skin, eyes - the list goes on. As with many health risks, the impacts are greater for those more vulnerable - the very young, the very old.

And it is particularly worrying that the risks stretch to those who aren't born yet. Pregnant women on board flights jeopardize the health of their fetus, but there is

simply a lack of awareness that this issue even exists - let alone how dangerous it really is. This is unacceptable and action must be taken to draw more attention to these risks as a matter of urgency.

From what I have learnt of the issue, it appears that there are five key areas that warrant immediate further attention. I've called them the five S's.

Science

The first is science - A lot of independent, peer-reviewed research has been undertaken in recent years which demonstrates that this is a genuine issue. But industry has been a step removed from this process, choosing to fund its own studies and often not asking the right questions. This detracts from the urgency of the situation and slows down progress to address the issue.

There is a need to do more research, we need to be asking the right questions, with methodologies suitable to provide sufficient answers and this process needs to be transparent. But as well as exploring what is in the air, we need a better understanding of what happens after exposure events - both chronic repeat exposure and leak events and we need to know more about the effects of a mixture of toxins. Above all, industry must engage with the findings.

Standards

Then we have standards - The standards that are in place are not up to the job. Whilst the containers of the substances used in the fuel contain health warnings, these warnings do not translate into passenger and crew safety information and this is a major oversight.

The current standards also do not address the complexity of the impact that a mixture of toxins may have when combined. They have not been tested under high altitude conditions. In some cases, benchmarks or exposure limits do not even exist - in short, they are entirely unfit for purpose.

Systems

The next issue is concerned with the systems in place

on the aircraft to both detect and warn against potential exposure. The regulations are clear, where there is a likely threat, detection and warning systems should be fitted to enable an informed response to the risk.

No airline has such equipment in place to address the potential exposure to heated engine oil fumes. This presents both occupational and public health liabilities and there is a moral and legal obligation here to address this shortcoming.

Solutions

But there are solutions - there are relatively simple technological fixes which would remove the problem entirely from the industry - the filtration system presented here at the conference represents a relatively low-cost measure that could be retrofitted onto the aircraft in use today. It would be a travesty for the industry to not take this solution seriously.

And as seen by the introduction of the Dreamliner, it is entirely possible to have a separate compressor for the cabin air, without needing to rely on bleed air at all. New craft should have this system fitted as standard.

Sharing

Finally, we need more sharing - This is a little-known issue, but that needs to change. Passengers and crew alike should be aware of the dangers that face them when boarding a flight. Whether we are talking about a leak event, or the low-level exposure that they are at risk of on any given craft to any given destination, people need to know. There is a need for a larger scale public awareness effort on this issue. Similarly, there needs to be more pressure put on decision-makers to act.

You have all taken the time to come and share your scientific knowledge, your expert opinions and your personal experiences, but where are EASA, where is the European Commission, where is the FAA, the airline CEOs and those responsible for ultimately ensuring the welfare of airline employees and the travelling public? They aren't here.

And it is this - more than anything - that stands in the way of making progress on all five of these areas. Industry and policymakers need to engage with this issue, be more open to change, be more transparent about the current situation and what needs to be done to rectify it.

As Professor Soskolne pointed out, we've seen with tobacco, asbestos, and countless other industries, change will come, but it will be a fight and it will take time. This issue has been unaddressed for far too long and the time to change is now.

The European Union enshrined the precautionary principle into law in 2012 and it is an approach which should certainly be used in this context. Even if we don't have all the answers and there are gaps in the science, if there is even a chance that the current system is leading to health impacts, especially long-term health impacts, then reasonable steps should be taken to mitigate against these risks. It is unacceptable for the industry to take any other stance on this.

CONCLUSIONS

As a member of the Transport and Tourism Committee in the European Parliament, I've been an active advocate of the need to urgently improve air quality across our towns and cities. And increasingly governments are starting to take the health threats posed by ambient air pollutants seriously. But it has been a hard battle and it is far from over.

Here, cleaning up the aviation industry does not only have to do with the urgent need to address the emissions created by the plane in the outside air, but the air being breathed inside too.

Thinking long term about the sustainability and health related challenges of the industry, both issues need to be taken much more seriously and I am committed to working with my fellow MEPs in Brussels to raise the profile of the issue and to lobby my peers to take action on this dangerous health threat as a priority.